

The Role of E-learning and its Impact on higher education: A survey on Rajshahi University students of Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Purpose- The main objective of this study is to explore the role of e-learning and its impact on higher education. Given the novelty of the experience, in this study, the researchers aim to investigate university students' perception and satisfaction regarding e-learning. The study also examines the importance of e-learning, identifies the problems faced by students while using e-learning and provides suggestions on how the university authority can improve e-learning more effectively. **Methods of the study** – Survey method was employed to understand the usage and impact of e-learning among the students at the University of Rajshahi in Bangladesh. Due to the pandemic situation of 2020, online social platforms were used and the questionnaires were circulated among 110 students from four departments of Social Science Faculty in Rajshahi University conveniently. **Findings** - The study shows that the overall feeling about e-

learning is a good and robust predictor of the students' overall satisfaction. The study examines that the majority of the students (51.8%) use e-learning for finding general information, and for accessing e-learning majority of the students (62.7%) always use the smartphone. Wi-Fi is more preferable to the students (47%) for accessing connection of e-learning. 58.2% of respondents identified Technical issues as the main problem of e-learning. **Limitations** - Rajshahi University is the second largest public University in Bangladesh where around 28000 students are studied in the postgraduate program in each year. In order to conduct this study only 110 students are regarded as sample and have come under investigation which remarks as the core limitation of this study. Besides, researchers and teachers play a vital role in this university. But they are not included as sample in this study. **Originality/value** – The paper contains original work regarding the role of e-learning and its impact on higher education among the students of Rajshahi University of Bangladesh and as such it will be useful for library professionals, administrators, and educators to develop suitable strategies as higher study institutions.

Keywords: E-learning, Higher Education, Technology, University Students, Bangladesh.

Prelude

Education is a light that shows mankind the right direction to surge. The purpose of education is not just to make a student literate but adds rational thinking, knowledgeable and selfsufficiency. When there is a willingness to change, there is hope for progress in any field. The use of technology to facilitate learning is accepted to be of value across educational institutions. E-learning includes all forms of electronically supported learning and teaching including Edutech. The Internet has become one of the vital ways to make available resources for research and learning for both teachers and students to share and acquire information (Richard and Haya, 2009). Technology-based e-learning encompasses the use of the internet and other important technologies to produce learning materials, teach learners, and also regulate courses in an organization (Fry, 2001). E-learning often involves both in the classroom and out of the classroom, educational experiences in technology, even as advances continue in regard to devices and curriculum (Kalaivani, 2014).

In Bangladesh the introduction and expansion of a range of e-learning tools has been initiating several changes in higher education institutions, particularly when it comes to their educational delivery and support processes. During the pandemic time, all educational activities of higher education institutes like Rajshahi University had been conducted its all academic functions through e-learning process. In this aspect this study has surveyed this university's students to know the role and impact of e-learning in their higher education while they pass their valuable time in their homes. E-learning is used here only as a tool to support the learning process.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective is to figure out the role of e-learning in higher education. The specific objectives are-

1. To find out the importance of e-learning
2. To investigate the impact of e-learning.
3. To identify the problem faced by students while using e-learning.

Significance of the study

This study is highly significant in establishing the role of e-learning in higher education. This information will help to avoid the barriers that are likely to hinder the development and expansion of e-learning in higher educational institutions. E-learning can also be seen as a promising way for improving the quality of higher education and the effectiveness of learning. It can give increased flexibility in the learning experience to the student, and enhances access to information resources for more students. E-learning could also lead to the enhancement of quality in higher education by leading to innovative pedagogical methods, new ways of learning and interacting by the easy sharing of the new practices among learners and teacher s communities, as well as by more transparency and easier comparison and crossfertilization of materials and methods. This research not only provides learning objectives but also evaluates the progress of the student and credit can be earned towards higher learning institutions.

Scope and Limitation

E-learning is a vast sector. This study can't cover all the e-learning system functionality. In developing countries, e-learning and other learning systems are affected by many reasons, such as economic factors. It is not possible to study all of the e-learning systems in higher education thoroughly. This study explains only how e-learning plays a role and impacts on students pursuing higher education. The other limitations of the study:

1. This study has been done only on four departments of Rajshahi University students.
2. Only the questionnaire technique is implemented for collecting data.
3. A small portion of the population (only 110 students) of RU is selected as a sample. Researchers and teachers are not included.

Methods of the study

This study is quantitative in nature. To investigate the objectives of this study, survey method was employed. The respondents were students of the University of Rajshahi. This study followed non-probability sampling procedure and the respondents were selected conveniently. From the population, only four departments of Social Science Faculty of Rajshahi University were selected purposively, such as Information Science and Library Management, Mass Communication and Journalism, Public Administration, and Social Work. The core data for this study has been collected through a structured questionnaire. Only close-ended questions are included in the questionnaire. Due to the pandemic situation using online social platforms the questionnaire was circulated among the students. A total of 130 questionnaires link were administered. 110 completed questionnaires of those who have used the e-learning platform recently were processed for the analysis. The data has been analyzed using SPSS, the Likert scale, and presented theoretically and graphically. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, percentage) were used to find out the overall satisfaction of the students and to explore the role of e-learning in higher education.

Literature Review

Babu and Sridevi (2018) investigate the importance of using e-learning in teaching in higher education. This study gives a scholarly background to the study by reviewing some contributions made by various researchers and institutions on the concept of e-learning, particularly its usage in teaching and learning in higher educational institutions.

Kakoty et al. (2011) analyze the importance of the education system and the recent market of e-learning procedures. This study shows that globalization of education, cross-culture aspects and culturally complex student support system in distance education as well as in e-learning environment is a prospective research area.

Panda and Mishra (2007) recommend that only an e-learning experience can change the faculty perceptions, therefore the faculty training program should preferably be designed and delivered on the web.

Ventatesh, et. al. (2003) conducts the key factors in the acceptance of e-learning as measured by behavioral intention to use the technology and actual usage in the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology.

Levin and Arafah (2002) remark on the differences between students who are highly gifted in internet usage and those who have had little opportunity to develop their experience with networking tools.

Dewar and Whittington (2000) discuss an experiment that looked at how adult learners make use of their MBTI type to cope with the challenges of learning in an online environment. The paper concludes that adult learners' learning styles can predict the pattern of their participation in online courses.

Kearsley (2000) notes that given instruction of equal quality, groups of students learning online generally achieve at levels equal to their peers in classrooms. Equality between the delivery systems has been well documented over decades for adult learners. E-learning- can improve how students learn, can improve what students learn, and can deliver high-quality learning opportunities to all children.

Why has E-learning become an important issue in academic institutions?

E-Learning is seen as a promising way for improving the quality of higher education and the effectiveness of learning (King & Boyatt, 2015). It can provide increased flexibility of learning experience to the student, enhances access to information resources for more students; harnesses the potential to drive innovative and effective ways of learning and teaching at very low marginal cost among the teachers and learners (Njenga & Fourie, 2010). E-Learning can also lead to the enhancement of quality in higher education by implementing innovative pedagogical methods, new ways of learning and interacting through the easy sharing of the new practices among learners and teachers communities as well as by more transparency, an easier comparison and cross-fertilization of materials and methods (Kalaivani, 2014).

It encompasses a field of integrated educational technologies. At one end are applications like PowerPoint, which have minimal impact on learning and teaching strategies for the organization. At the other end are virtual learning environments (VLEs), and managed learning environments (MLEs), which can have a significant impact on learning and teaching strategies, and on the organization (Julian et. al, 2005). According to Sanga views the continuum of e-learning as the educational technology from the supplemental use of technology in the Classroom, through blended or hybrid uses comprising a mix of face-toface and fully online instruction, to fully online synchronous and asynchronous distance learning environments delivered to remote learners (Sanga Lwoga & Sife, 2007))

The increased use of e-learning among educational institutions has led to a change in higher education (Abou El-Seoud, et.al, 2014). One of the main reasons for this is it gives students greater access to education in comparison to traditional methods of teaching as students can undertake

their study from anywhere and at any time as well as being given the option to study part-time or full-time (Ellis, Ginns, & Piggott 2009). E-learning has transformed the educational sector by enabling students to share information and data in a relatively easy way. That’s why E-learning is considered as an important part of academic institutions day by day.

Data analysis and interpretation

Table 1 describes the department wise distribution of respondents. Out of 110 students, 44.5% respondents were selected from Information Science and Library Management, 20% respondents were from Mass Communication and Journalism, 17.3% respondents were from Social Work and 18.2% respondents were from Public Administration in Rajshahi University.

Table 1: Department-wise distributed respondents

Department Name	No of respondents	Percentage %
Information science and Library Management	49	44.5%
Mass Communication and Journalism	22	20.0%
Social Work	19	17.3%
Public Administration	20	18.2%
Total	110	100%

Figure 1 shows the students usage of the connection for accessing e-learning. According to this figure we can see that 3.6% students used Broadband, Only 1.8% students used both Broadband and Wi-Fi but 6.4% students used Broadband, Wi-Fi, and Cellular Data. More students i.e. 20.9% used Cellular Data while 1.8% students used modem, Broadband, Wi-Fi, and Cellular data. The majority of the students used Wi-Fi 47% and 17.3% students used both Wi-Fi and cellular data. So, it can be said that, Wi-Fi is more preferable to the students for accessing connection of e-learning.

Figure 1: Connection used by respondents for accessing e-learning.

From Table 2 it is observed that most of the students (67.3%) used e-learning less than three hours in a week, only 1.8% students used more than 10+ hours per week, 20.9% students used 3-5 hours per week and only 10% students used 5-7 hours per week.

Table 2: Time spent for using e-learning.

Time spent (week)	Number of respondents	Percentage %
1-3 hours	74	67.3%
10+ hours	2	1.8%
3-5 hours	23	20.9%
5-7 hours	11	10.0%
Total=	110	100%

From Table 2 it is observed that most of the students (67.3%) used e-learning less than three hours in a week, only 1.8% students used more than 10+ hours per week, 20.9% students used 3-5 hours per week and only 10% students used 5-7 hours per week.

Table 3: Electronic devices used for accessing e-learning

Electronic devices	Never		Rarely		Sometimes		Very often		Always		Mean	SD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Computer	55	50.0%	21	19.1%	22	20.0%	8	7.3%	4	3.6%	1.95	1.152
Laptop	23	20.9%	17	15.5%	40	36.4%	19	17.3%	11	10.0%	2.80	1.240
Smart Phone	22	20.0%	5	4.5%	27	24.5%	9	8.2%	69	62.7%	4.29	.989
Tablet	89	80.9%	9	8.2%	8	7.3%	3	2.7%	1	0.9%	1.35	.806

Table 3 analyses the usage of electronic device by the respondents to access e-learning. Only 3.6% of the respondents always used computers. It indicates that these users don't feel comfortable to do the work with computers. While 7.3% of the respondents used very often 20.0% respondents used computer sometimes, 19.1% of the respondents used rarely and 50.0% used computer for accessing e-learning. The Mean (M) is 1.95 and the Standard Deviation (SD) is 1.152. On the other hand 10.0% of the respondents used Laptop always, 17.3% of the respondents used this very often, 36.4% of the respondents used laptop sometimes, 15.5% of the respondents used rarely and 20.9% of the respondents never used laptop for accessing e-learning. The Mean is 2.80,

and the Standard Deviation is 1.20. Majority percentage 62.7% of respondents used smart phone always, 8.2% of the respondents used this very often, 24.5% of the respondents used smart phone sometimes, 4.5% of the respondents used rarely and 20.0% of the respondents never used smart phone for accessing e-learning. The Mean is 4.29 and the Standard Deviation is 0.989. 0.9% of the respondents used tablets always, 2.7% used very often, 7.3% used sometimes, 8.2% of the respondents used rarely and the highest percentage 80.9% of the respondents never used this technology.

The Mean is 1.35 and the Standard Deviation is 0.806. The percentage shows multiple responses.

Table 4: Managing cost by students

Managing cost	No. of respondents	Percentage %
By tuition	12	10.9%
Freelancing	5	4.5%
From parents	71	64.5%
From parents, By tuition	5	4.5%
From parents, By tuition, Through part time job	1	0.9%
From parents, freelancing	3	2.7%
From parents, Others	2	1.8%
From parents, Through part time job	1	0.9%
From parents, Through part time job, Others	1	0.9%
Others	6	5.5%
Through part time job	3	2.7%

Table 4 reveals that the highest percentage (64.5%) of the respondents manage the cost from parents most. It is also observed that 10.9% of the respondents manage cost by tuition the most. 5.5% of the respondents manage the cost through other sources. It is clear that 4.5% of the respondents manage the cost through freelancing and also from parents and by tuition. Only 2.7% of the respondents manage from parents and freelancing and also part-time jobs. The lowest percentage 0.9% of the respondents manage costs from three sources like from parents, by tuition, through part-time job; from parents, through part-time job and from parents, through part-time job, others.

Table 5: Purpose of using e-learning

Purpose	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	SD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
For finding general information	6	5.5%	2	1.8%	26	23.6%	57	51.8%	19	17.3%	3.74	.955
For research	4	3.6%	10	9.1%	31	28.2%	47	42.7%	18	16.4%	3.59	.989
For class note	2	1.8%	7	6.4%	26	23.6%	46	41.8%	29	26.4%	3.85	.950
For job opportunity	7	6.4%	7	6.4%	24	21.8%	52	47.3%	20	18.2%	3.65	1.054
Others	6	5.5%	10	9.1%	37	33.6%	40	36.4%	17	15.5%	3.47	1.038

Table 5 reveals the purpose of using e-learning for the respondents. It is noted from this table that 17.3% of the respondents were strongly agreed for finding general information, 51.8% of the respondents were agreed, 23.6% respondents were neutral about this statement, 1.8% of the respondents disagree and 5.5% of the respondents were strongly disagreed. The mean value of all the variables is 3.74 and SD is 0.955. It is clear that 16.4% of the respondents were strongly agreed with the research, 42.7% of the respondents were agreed with this purpose, 28.2% of the respondents were neutral, 9.1% of the respondents disagreed and 3.6% of the respondents were strongly disagree with the use of e-learning for research. The mean value of all the variables is 3.59 and SD is 0.989. 26.4% of the respondents were strongly agreed for the purpose of class notes, 41.8% of the respondents were agreed, 23.6% of the respondents were neutral, 6.4% of the respondents were disagreed and 1.8% of the respondents were strongly disagreed with class notes. The mean value of all the variables is 3.85 and SD is 0.950. It is also observed that 18.2% of the respondents were strongly agreed for the purpose of job opportunity, 47.3% of the respondents were agreed, 21.8% of the respondents were neutral, 6.4% of the respondents were disagreed and also strongly disagreed with job opportunity. The mean value of all the variables is 3.65 and SD is 1.054. According to the result of table 5 it can be said that 15.5% of the respondents were strongly agreed for other purpose, 36.4% of the respondents were agreed, 33.6% of the respondents were neutral, 9.1% of the respondents were disagreed and 5.5% of the respondents were strongly disagree with the use of e-learning for others. The mean value of all the variables is 3.47 and SD is 1.038.

Figure 2: Experience in using e-learning

It is evident from figure 1 that the majority percentage (30%) respondents used e-learning from 2 to 3 years, 22.7% respondents used it from 1 to 2 years, 19.1% respondents used it from up to 1 year, and 28.2% respondents used e-learning for more than 4 years.

Table 6: Role of e-learning in higher education

Role of E-learning	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	SD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	E-learning is for everyone	6	5.5%	14	12.7%	15	13.6%	47	42.7%	28		
Quick Delivery of Lessons	2	1.8%	6	5.5%	21	19.1%	54	49.1%	27	24.5%	3.89	.902
Provide Consistency	3	2.7%	9	8.2%	31	28.2%	50	45.5%	17	15.5%	3.63	.937
Effectiveness	4	3.6%	7	6.4%	27	24.5%	44	40.0%	28	25.5%	3.77	1.020
Less Impact on Environment	4	3.6%	15	13.6%	32	29.1%	43	39.1%	16	14.5%	3.47	1.020

Table 6 shows the role of e-learning in higher education. Majority of the respondents (42.7%) was agreed with the statement e-learning is for everyone, 25.5% of the respondents were strongly agreed, and 13.6% were neutral, 12.7% were disagreed and 5.5% were strongly disagreed. The mean value of all the variables is 3.70 and Standard Deviation is 1.146. It is cleared that 49.1% of the respondents indicated their agreement with the point quick delivery of lessons. 24.5% were strongly agreed, and 19.1% were neutral, 5.5% were disagreed and 1.8% were strongly disagreed. The mean value of all the variables is 3.89 and Standard Deviation is 0.902. It is noted that 45.5% of the respondents were agreed with the point provide consistency. 15.5% were strongly agreed,

28.2% were neutral, 8.2% were disagreed and 2.7% were strongly disagreed. The mean value of all the variables is 3.63 and Standard Deviation is 0.937. 40.0% of the respondents were agreed with the role of effectiveness, 25.5% were strongly agreed with this comment 24.5% preferred to be remain neutral, 6.4% were disagreed and 3.6% were strongly disagreed. The mean value of all the variables is 3.77 and Standard Deviation is 1.020. Also 39.1% of respondent were agreed and 14.5% were strongly agreed with the fifth statement less impact on environment, while 13.6% were disagreed, 3.6% were strongly disagreed and 29.1% remained neutral. The mean value of all the variables is 3.47 and the Standard Deviation is 1.020.

Table 7: Enjoying e-learning by students

Enjoy	No of respondents	Percentage %
No, not at all	4	3.6%
No, there are quite a few challenges	21	19.1%
Yes, absolutely	59	53.6%
Yes, but I would like to change a few things	26	23.6%
Total	110	100%

Table 7 presents a clear idea of students' enjoyment or not enjoy with e-learning. 53.6% of students said that they enjoy e-learning, and 23.6% of students enjoyed e-learning but they would like to change a few things. On the other hand 19.1% students said against enjoyment because they faced few challenges and 3.6% students said not at all.

Table 8: Advantages of e-learning

Advantages of e-learning	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mea n	SD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	Learning from own home	4	3.6%	6	5.5%	14	12.7%	54	49.1%	32		
Everything in the same place	3	2.7%	8	7.3%	22	20.0%	48	43.6%	29	26.4%	3.84	.991
Easy access to information	3	2.7%	9	8.2%	22	20.0%	51	46.4%	25	22.7%	3.78	.980
Freedom of choosing teaching materials	2	1.8%	10	9.1%	26	23.6%	50	45.5%	22	20.0%	3.73	.947
Lower cost of study	8	7.3%	14	12.7%	22	20.0%	49	44.5%	17	15.5%	3.48	1.123
Special ideas	3	2.7%	5	4.5%	27	24.5%	59	53.6%	16	14.5%	3.73	.866
No need to read printed book	15	13.6%	22	20.0%	23	20.9%	38	34.5%	12	10.9%	3.09	1.238

Analysis of the table 8 reveals the advantage of e-learning from students' perspective. About the first advantage "Learning from own home" of 29.1% said strongly agree and 49.1% said agree, 12.7% remained neutral, 5.5% said disagree and 3.6% said strongly disagree with it. The mean value is 3.95 and the standard deviation is 0.985. 26.4% of students were strongly agreed and 43.6% were agreed with the 2nd advantage of "Everything in the same place". 20.0% were neutral 7.3% were disagreed and 2.7% were strongly disagreed with it. The mean value is 3.84 and the standard deviation is 0.991. We also see that 22.7% of students were strongly agreed, 46.4% were agreed, 20.0% were neutral, 8.2% were disagreed and 2.7% were strongly disagreed with the advantage of "Easy access to information". The mean value is 3.78 and the standard deviation is 0.980. 20.0% of students were agreed and 45.5% were strongly agreed with the advantage of "Freedom of choosing teaching materials". 23.6% were neutral and 9.1% were disagreed and 1.8% was strongly disagreed with it. The mean value is 3.73 and the standard deviation is 0.947. 15.5% of students said strongly agree, 44.5% said agree, 20.0% said neutral 12.7% said disagree and 7.3% said strongly disagree with the advantage of "Lower cost of study". The mean value is 3.48 and the standard deviation is 1.123. Other side a high percentage 53.6% of the students said agree and

14.5% said strongly agree, 24.5% said neutral, 4.5% said disagree and 2.7% said strongly disagree with the advantage of “Special ideas”. The mean value is 3.73 and the standard deviation is 0.866.

Regarding the last advantage “No need to read printed book” 10.9% said strongly agree, 34.5% said agree, 20.9% were neutral, 20.9% were disagreed and 13.6% were strongly disagreed. The mean value is 3.09 and the standard deviation is 1.238.

Table 9: Problems faced when it comes to e-learning

Problems	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	SD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	Adaptability (learners take time to adapt to the new style)	9	8.2%	9	8.2%	19	17.3%	57	51.8%	16		
Distractions (many chances of deviating from other activities like social media)	6	5.5%	8	7.3%	23	20.9%	58	52.7%	15	13.6%	3.44	1.009
Technical Issue	5	4.5%	7	6.4%	15	13.6%	64	58.2%	19	17.3%	3.23	1.139
Computer Knowledge	6	5.5%	15	13.6%	18	16.4%	52	47.3%	19	17.3%	3.45	1.114
Lack of motivation and support	7	6.4%	15	13.6%	16	14.5%	57	51.8%	15	13.6%	3.52	1.147
Time Management.	7	6.4%	14	12.7%	18	16.4%	53	48.2%	18	16.4%	3.64	1.056

Table 9 indicates some problems which are faced by students when it comes to e-learning. 14.5% of students said strongly agree, 51.8% said agree, 17.3% said neutral, 8.2% said disagree and also strongly agree with the problem of “Adaptability (learners take time to adapt to the new style)”. The mean value is 3.62 and the standard deviation is 1.149. 13.6% said strongly agree and 52.7% were agreed, 20.9% were neutral, 7.3% said disagree and 5.5% said strongly disagree with the problem of “Distractions (many chances of deviating from other activities like social media)”. The mean value is 3.44 and the standard deviation is 1.009. In Technical Issue problem 17.3% opined for strongly agree, 58.2% opined for agree, 13.6% were neutral and 6.4% opined for disagree and 4.5% opined for strongly disagree. The mean value is 3.23 and the standard deviation is 1.139. Other wise 17.3% of students said strongly agree, 47.3% said agree, 16.4% said neutral, 13.6% said disagree and 5.5% said strongly agree with the problem of “Computer Knowledge”. The mean

value is 3.45 and the standard deviation is 1.114. In “Lack of motivation and support” aspect the top score 51.8% belongs to agree. The mean value is 3.52 and the standard deviation is 1.147. In “Time management” aspect the top score 48.2% goes to also agree. The mean value is 3.64 and the standard deviation is 1.056. 14.5% of students said strongly agree, 51.8% said agree, 17.3% said neutral, 8.2% said disagree and also strongly agree with the problem of “Adaptability (learners take time to adapt to the new style)”. The mean value is 3.62 and the standard deviation is 1.149. 18 students agree and 19 students strongly agree with the problem of “Computer Knowledge”. 18 students are neutral and 15 students disagree with it. The mean value is 3.45 and the standard deviation is 1.114 on the other hand 57 students agree and 15 students strongly agree with the problem of “Lack of motivation and support”. 16 students are neutral and 15 students disagree with it. The mean value is 3.52 and the standard deviation is 1.147.

Table 10: Satisfaction level of using e-learning

Satisfaction level	No of respondents	Percentage %
Dissatisfied	11	10.0%
Neutral	23	20.9%
Satisfied	63	57.3%
Very dissatisfied	1	0.9%
Very satisfied	12	10.9%
Total	110	100%

The collected data of table 10 indicates the satisfaction level of respondents regarding the quality and quantity of e-learning. 57% of respondents agreed that they were satisfied with these. 10.9% respondents were very satisfied with the quality and quantity of e-learning, and 20.9% of respondents agreed that they were neutral with these. But 10.0% of respondents were dissatisfied with the e-learning system. And only 0.9% respondent was very dissatisfied.

Major findings of the study

- 47.3% of the respondent used Wi-Fi for accessing e-learning.
- Majority of the respondents (67.3%) used e-learning less than 3 hours per week 3. For accessing e-learning 62.7% of respondents used their smart phones always.
- The majority of the respondents (64.4%) managed the cost from parents.
- The majority of the respondents 51.8% mostly used e-learning for finding general information.
- 30% of respondents used e-learning for 2 to 3 years.

- 42.7% of respondents agreed that e-learning is for everyone and 49.1% of respondents agreed that e-learning can provide quick delivery of lessons.
- 53.6% of respondents enjoyed e-learning.
- 49.1% of respondents thought that “learning from own home” is the main advantage of e-learning
- 58.2% of respondents agreed that the main problem of e-learning is “Technical Issues”.
- 57% of respondents agreed that they are satisfied with the quantity and quality of e-learning.

Recommendations

The following actions will improve e-learning more effectively in higher educational institutions-

1. Should increase the availability of hardware (particularly computers) that can be made speedy access to e-learning.
2. Should provide faster internet connectivity/improved bandwidth
3. Should improve proper e-learning software.
4. University should motivate in awareness rising about the value of e-learning
5. Institutions and academic units should provide and actively promote training for students in the use of technologies that students will use in their courses.
6. To solve the problem of frequent power cuts and connectivity necessary steps should be taken by the university authority.

Conclusion

The environment of higher education is evolving all over the world. Rising costs, shrinking budgets and an increasing need for e-education have made educational institutions reexamine the way that education has been delivered. In response to this changing environment, e-learning is being implemented more and more frequently in higher education, creating new and exciting opportunities for both educational institutions and students. E-learning involves the use of digital tools for teaching and learning. It involves the training, delivery of knowledge, motivating students to interact with each other, as well as exchanging and respecting different point of views. Higher Education institutes in developing countries possess basic ICT infrastructures, such as Local Area Network (LAN), internet, computers, video, audio, CDs and DVDs, and mobile technology facilities that form the basis for the establishment of e-learning. Pedagogical, technical and cost

issues should be taken into account for each specific technology when integrating ICTs in teaching and learning practices. The study has tried to explain the role of e-learning in particular and it has shown that despite the challenges discussed, the value and the need for effective application of e-learning is of great significance to an effective higher education structure because of its strong impact in teaching and learning. The present higher education system plays a vital role in individual and societal development. So higher educational institutions need to have suitable strategies in place for the successful deployment of the e-learning process, with the aim of developing the student, society, and the nation (Das, 2021).

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